

OPPORTUNITIES FOR USING A PERSONALIZED APPROACH TO DEVELOP STUDENTS' ACADEMIC WRITING SKILLS

Tabarak N.,

Teacher of English

NIS of Physics and Mathematics

Turgumbayeva B.

Teacher of English

NIS of Physics and Mathematics

Abstract

The article reflects the current issues of the implementation of personalized learning, taking into account the characteristics of generation Z, and is aimed at developing academic writing skills and realizing the potential of students.

Keywords: Z-generation peculiarities, personalized learning, self-regulation, feedup, feedback, feedforward, action research, intervention, academic writing.

Implementing personalized learning approach through development of academic writing skills of the Z-generation Learner

The question of implementing personalized learning approach is one of the urgent tasks of the modern educational process. Current students are representatives of the generation of zoomers who have a tendency to individualism, self-study which is a beneficial ground for the implementation of personalized and individualized learning. To determine the research question, it was decided to study the intellectual needs of learners.

Thus, the initial rationale for the choice of the research question was the following features of Generation Z:

- safety and interest come first
- they consider and evaluate the importance what they do and for what they do it, they need concrete knowledge to implement today's tasks
- want practicality and quick results “Now and Here”; think globally and crave live communication (M. Klarin)
- high learning speed (not only the number of days, hours, but also to speed up the flow of information, time to solve problems, respond faster to the result) [1]

The second reason is “the clip thinking of zoomers – they think in short-term perspectives and are not ready to wait; do not think about the future, since the present is changing too quickly, and there are no more ready-made solutions, which leads to the inability to systematically perceive information, think analytically and express one's thoughts thoroughly.

They do not accept hierarchy and authority, because in the digital world all people are equal. According to zoomers, the personal qualities of a person deserve respect, and not his age and status. Another characteristic is that they want to study and complete tasks on their own schedule; do not strive to over fulfill the plan and set ambitious goals. They have weakened imagination, reflection and understanding of the text. They remember only the necessary things, which have practical significance.” [2]

Considering the characteristic features of generation Z, it became necessary to think over effective principles, methods and strategies for the productive improvement of the educational process. A personalized learning approach requires the teacher to be a mentor, navigator, facilitator and act as an emotional leader when interacting with students. It is mandatory to include pedagogical technologies for the development of critical thinking, cultivate the culture to reflect on strengths and what needs to be worked on, and develop research skills.

It is recommended to structure the learning process, provide feedback, and develop skills for independent work with resources. Also, use the possibilities of practice-oriented digital technologies: involving students in content creation, modular training (the ability to independently combine training modules, enable students to choose techniques and methods, an algorithm of actions for the implementation of educational tasks).

A detailed analysis of the psychophysiological peculiarities of generation Z, and studying of students' preparation requirements for the External Examination enabled to identify research question:

What strategies and techniques of personalized learning approach enable to develop writing academic skills?

Based on the topic of the study, the following tasks were determined:

1. Collect and analyze data based on the results of a diagnostic test on aspects of listening, reading and writing (Opinion essay).
2. Study educational resources on writing academic text, review the literature on research conducted in this direction.
3. Conduct students' reflection on writing academic ielts essay, identifying strengths, weaknesses and learning difficulties.
4. Organize educational work based on the results of the analysis and the data obtained.

5. Determine the optimal strategies, techniques and methods that will allow to implement personalized learning approach and develop academic writing skills.

In the course of the study, at the stage of analyzing the written works of students (Opinion essay) we came

to the conclusion that students have difficulty with creating a thesis statement: there is no general understanding what thesis statement is, the inability to formulate it with arguments in accordance with the requirement of an effective thesis. The analysis of the works also made it possible to identify a number of features in students in writing an academic essay. Thus, three groups of students with different levels of academic writing skills were identified: for one group of students, thesis clichés were used, for the second - matrix formulas, and the third group of students created thesis relying on their previous knowledge and learning experience.

After studying the reflective records of students, the following difficulties were identified: inability to analyze the essay question and its task determine the type of academic essay and select the appropriate thesis form to answer the essay question. Also, students experienced difficulties in using high-level academic vocabulary: 20% of students continue to use A2-B1 level vocabulary, 65%, being in the ZPD (zone of proximal development) use B1+ level vocabulary, and 15% effectively operate with B2 level vocabulary.

Diagram 1

In addition, students' written works showed the need to use advanced grammatical structures such as Complex and Compound sentences, Passive voice, Conditionals, Inversion, which is one of the criteria for effective writing of academic essay.

One of the equally important requirements for academic writing is the ability to logically convey thoughts, which was partly absent in some girls' papers due to their emotional characteristics. The discovery was interesting: boys have a logic of thoughts, but vocabulary suffers, girls have the opposite situation.

Based on the results of the analysis and in the course of conducting action research, the following techniques and strategies were identified, which enabled to achieve positive results:

1. Determining the type of essay through analyzing the essay task + Determining the form of the thesis through the analysis of the question. We have developed this task, which allowed students to improve this skill:

Table 1

Task: Analyze essay questions and match with suitable type of essay and identify relevant Thesis statement:

Type of the question	Type of essay	Thesis statement formula
1. Essay question: <i>In many countries, children are becoming overweight and unhealthy. Some people think that the government has the responsibility to solve this problem. To what extent do you agree or disagree?</i>	A. For and Against essay	A. State 1 or 2 problems and possible solutions
2. Essay question: <i>The exceed amount of time adolescents spend in the virtual world forces them to get devices addicted and make them glued to the screens. To what issues does it lead and what are possible solution?</i>	B. Opinion essay	B. State one or two For-reasons and refer to Against-reasons briefly
3. Essay question: <i>Virtual world - a blessing or a curse. Discuss pros and cons.</i>	C. Problem and Solution essay	C. Qualification + state your opinion + 2 reasons for your opinion

Key: 1. B C
2. C A
3. A B

1. Coming from theory and rules to examples, or from analysis of examples to independent definition of rules, formulas, matrices, has become one of the effective strategies for implementing personalized learning approach.

The learning resources developed for this purpose are listed below.

Thesis statement for academic essay

A thesis statement is the most important sentence in your IELTS writing task 2 answer. It is contained in the introduction and each introduction should have one.

A thesis statement is your main idea: it gives answer to the essay question. It tells the examiner that you have understood the question and it will lead to a clearer, more coherent essay.

A good thesis statement goes towards getting a good band score in the writing section.

For and Against essay

Thesis statement: state one or two *For-reasons* and refer to *Against-reasons* briefly

Essay question: *Virtual world - a blessing or a curse. Discuss pros and cons.*

1. **Thesis statement:** *The most vital benefit of the cyber world is its positive influence on revolution in technology and medicine, and the drawbacks of that are non-effective and inhumane use.*
2. **Thesis statement:** *The major beneficial sides of computer use are the amount of information instantly available to students and the ability to communicate with other students. However, there are some drawbacks such as the lack of discipline and motivation provided by computers.*

Picture 1. Worksheet - «Studying route»

2. Use the thesis generator [3] to formulate it correctly in order to answer the essay question. Thus, students found out that the answer to the essay question lies in the thesis, and it is the most important criterion for an academic essay - *Task response*.

Thesis Generator

1. **What is your topic?**
 - Who's to blame for the obesity epidemic?
2. **What is your stance or claim?**
 - Parents should teach their children healthy eating habits.
3. **What is your rationale for this stance?**
 - ...because parents are the first to teach and model healthy eating habits.
4. **What concessions will you make to qualify your stance and acknowledge opposition?**
 - ...although some want to blame the fast food industry for the obesity epidemic.
5. **Qualification + Stance + Rationale = Thesis**
 - Although some blame the fast food industry for the obesity epidemic, parents are more at fault because they are the first to teach and model healthy eating habits to their children.

Picture 2

<http://mrsrooney.pbworks.com/w/page/114236949/Thesis%20Statement>

Works of students affirm different levels of mental activity and the ability to express thoughts in writing: *confident autonomous student (group A), independent student (Group C), relatively independent ZPD (zone of proximal development – Group B), less independent ZPD.*

Student 1 Group A

In the contemporary realities, it is definitely obvious that urbanization is taking place. Even so, residing the rural area still attracts many people's attention, considering its benefits and drawbacks. Said differently, this essay is going to highlight the serenity of such lifestyle as an exact advantage, and a possible ~~consequence~~ ~~disadvantage~~ loneliness as a disadvantage of inhabiting the countryside.

Student 2 Group A

In our time young generation have unrestricted access to the gadgets and social networks to communicate with people. This essay will suggest that the biggest problem caused by unlimited access to the Internet is Internet addiction and show that the best solution for this situation is limit ^{for} social networks and focus on real live.

Picture 3. Works of group A students "confident autonomous student": rely on their previous knowledge and learning experience

Student 1 Group B

Nowadays, (the) some people would that students need to (do) (the) school uniforms while others on the contrary, think that students should be free to wear their clothes. I neither agree nor disagree with this statement, because such as school uniforms and they do this have one advantage and disadvantage. Thesis is unappropriate for this type of essay.

Student 2 Group B

Topic number: 1
More and more people are thinking that today's adolescents have more problems than their parents. I absolutely agree (the) statement with this statement, because teenagers suffer from many ^{both} psychological and emotional problems. Thesis: a 5★.

Picture 4. Works of group B students (girls) – "relatively independent" in ZPD, used thesis formula (generator) and successfully enhanced writing academic skills

Student 1 Group C

It's is often held, that nowadays teenagers have more stressful lives, than other old groups and I disagree with this statement, because regardless of age every person can experience stress. Thesis: a 5★
More and more adults ^{some} say, that ^{claim}

Student 2 Group C

which can be threatening for children.
Discuss the topic and suggest a possible way out. to socialize with others people
Many kids have limitless access to the Internet. This can lead to dangerous situations which can be threatening for them. This essay will first suggest that the biggest problem caused by unrestricted access to the Internet is ^{and} ~~changing of~~ relationships and real communication with real people in real life is the most feasible viable solution. ^{pro} obstacle ~~is~~ with socialisation in real life and live communication with other people ^{and develop the communication skills} is the most viable solution.

Picture 5. Works of group C Students – "independent student" who used matrix formulas, with the help of which they improved writing skills for creating thesis statement

3. Reasoning and presenting relevant arguments in Problem and Solution essay, it is necessary to emphasize the existing problem and propose a solution to this problem by appropriately arranging the arguments in one complex thesis sentence, which is demonstrated by Students A1 and Student A2 - a confident autonomous student in their essay.

Student 1 Group A

that is not recommended. This essay will discuss destructive content in Internet as the first and foremost (danger) in social networking system and suggest parental control as a possible resolution.

Student 2 Group A

situations that may harm them. This essay will discuss the problem of unsupervised surfing (through) the Internet and suggest traffic monitoring as a reliable, but very extreme solution.

Picture 6

4. Using formulas, matrices and various clichés to write the main part of the essay. For this purpose, check-lists for each type of essay were created for the individual work of students and to provide Feed-back and Feed-forward

Check-list

4	<p>Intro</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - general overview on the topic - paraphrase/restate the question - thesis statement: state one or two For-reasons and refer to Against-reasons briefly 	
5	<p>Well-developed “For” paragraph: Argument(s) in favour</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topic sentence – statement about pros (UE: complex or compound sentence) <i>Ex. Gr.: With respect to ... (topic you discuss=Noun/Gerund) several pro arguments can be mentioned.</i> <p>Justification of arguments:</p> <p>Explain – providing reasons, examples, facts describe details of the “Pros” through “5-Wh?”: <i>What is/are pros?</i> <i>Who, where, when, how ...experience the pros/benefits?</i> <i>What is/are the result/s of the pros/benefits?</i></p> <p>Example – give a specific example to illustrate the main points</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use Facts, Statistics (include people, time, place, specific numbers) - Use 2 modes of argumentation: Logos and Ethos <p>The concluding sentence of each paragraph should function as a hook and transition into the next paragraph.</p>	

Picture 7

5. Writing the final part of the essay logically reflecting the introductory part of the essay.

7	<p>Conclusion – stating your opinion either directly or indirectly and providing a balanced view of the topic. You can provide closure to your essay, giving the reader something to think about. So what?/ give a summary of the topic and give your opinion/ restate thesis statement.</p> <p><i>Or, use the matrix:</i></p> <p><i>As you can see there is a terrible problem of _____ in _____ today.</i></p> <p>OR...It is clear that the issue is urgent and needs in immediate solution. The most feasible/viable/sustainable/workable solution is</p> <p>Summarize the essay by showing a balanced view rather than a subjective opinion, rely on the facts covered in the body paragraphs.</p> <p><i>Sample for Conclusion</i></p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">The conclusion is that Internet communication should complement life and not be the basic of all our activities! Social networks can bring many benefits. Abuse of public can lead to dependence, loss of attention, waste of time, alienation and stupefaction. Social networks are both good and bad. It is our power to take from them only the good and to weed out the bad.</p>	
---	---	--

Picture 8

A detailed study of the structure, content, requirements for effective essay writing, and the practice of its writing, also made it possible to find and define a number of other strategies for solving the issue. First, independent analysis of written works and reflection on these works gave students the opportunity to study their own mistakes and identify weaknesses of writing skills.

Secondly, autonomous work with learning resources allowed students to develop critical thinking:

they made their first discoveries in writing academic papers, developed the skills of analysis and synthesis aimed at improving academic writing. Also, the autonomous work of students made it possible to develop leadership skills, where there was a need to give effective Feedback and Feedforward. For this purpose, the following system was used [3].

Picture 9

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/The-impact-of-using-Socratic-based-formative-to-in-Hussein/8e120df79b1e98bce26476a16ec52c5fcdaf3195>

The feedback received during the intervention and upon completion of the work and reflection of students indicates an increase in the level of independence and self-regulation skills in students due to the techniques, strategies, as well as selected and created resources.

Diagram 2

Diagram 3

What impede the research?

In the course of the study, we encountered such difficulties as different requirements for written work in three language subjects: Kazakh, Russian and English. Thus, for example, according to the criteria for writing academic writing in Russian, one of the descriptors is as follows: “Use a rhetorical question”, while in English this is unacceptable.

Also, the task was to work out writing skills in six types of writing with different requirements in one academic year, which became an overload for students. Moreover, the students were overwhelmed by the preparation for the external exam in six subjects, where there was also intensive preparation. It should be taken into account that the first quarter was less productive due to the adaptive period to the learning process after online learning.

The work done in the frame of action research, determining the quality and productivity of the selected methods, techniques, strategies and educational resources, made it possible to find the answer to the research question: the use of the thesis-cliché, thesis-matrix, the use of checklists contribute to the development of the ability to logically answer the question of an academic essay and structure it effectively.

References

1. Klarin M.V. Innovations in World Pedagogy: Exploration-Based Learning, Play and Discussion (Analysis of foreign experience) – Riga, ... “Experiment”, 1995 – 176 p

2. Innovations in World Pedagogy: Exploration-Based Learning, Play and Discussion (Analysis of foreign experience) - Riga, SPC "Experiment", 1995 - 176 p.

3. https://pedlib.ru/Books/7/0030/7_0030-1.shtml

4. Pestereva O.A. “Generation Z Learning Features: Problems and Solutions”, Ulan-Ude, 2021 <https://www.bsu.ru/content/page/21087/4-osobnosti-obucheniya-%C2%ABpokoleniya-Z%C2%BB-problemi-i-puti-resheniya.PDF>

5. Thesis Statement <http://mrs-rooney.pbworks.com/w/page/114236949/Thesis%20Statement>

6. Douglas Fisher, Nancy Frey Feed Up, Back, Forward <https://www.ascd.org/el/articles/feed-up-back-forward>

7. «Z Generation Z: how to educate» <https://lala.lanbook.com/pokolenie-z-kak-ego-uchit>

8. «Исследование учителем собственной практики Мұғалімнің өз тәжірибесін зерттеуі», Библиотека Центра Педагогического Мастерства, 2015 <https://wku.edu.kz/images/usm/psixolog/sob-prakt.pdf>

9. Коатс Дж. Поколения и стили обучения /Дж. Коатс. — М.: МАПДО — Новочеркасск: НОК, 2011

10. Thesis Statement <http://mrs-rooney.pbworks.com/w/page/114236949/Thesis%20Statement>